

DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGY AND EQUIPMENT TO IMPROVE THE RECLAIM STATE OF SALT SOILS

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Introduction. In the world, the development of technologies and technical means to improve the ameliorative state of saline soil occupies a leading position. "Given that on a global scale 44-46 percent of the sown area allocated for agricultural crops are saline to varying degrees", the development of chisel rippers used to improve the reclamation state of lands with dense and gypsum soil layers, as well as technical means for laying mole drains on lands with high groundwater levels is considered an important task. From this point of view, much attention is paid to the production of machines and units for loosening lands with dense and gypsum soil layers, and on saline lands for laying molehill drains [1,2].

Research work is being carried out in the world aimed at developing new scientific and technical foundations for technologies for loosening dense and gypsum layers, laying molehill drains under the arable layer of saline soils and technical means for their implementation. In this direction, including the development of design schemes for a chisel ripper for loosening dense and gypsum layers of soil and devices for creating mole drains under the arable layer, as well as the rationale for technological processes that ensure resource saving of the working parts of the chisel ripper when loosening dense and gypsum layers and when laying molehill drains under the arable layer of saline soils, it becomes important. At the same time, it is considered necessary to produce a resource-saving chisel cultivator that loosens dense and gypsum soil layers with a poor reclamation condition, as well as a device that forms molehill drains to remove groundwater [3,4].

Large-scale measures are being taken in the Republic to reduce energy consumption in agricultural production, improve the reclamation state of lands, grow agricultural plants based on advanced technologies and produce high-performance reclamation machines, pay special attention to the production of technical means that provide, with the lowest energy consumption, quality -

implementation of the processes of loosening dense and gypsum soil layers, laying molehill drains in saline soils. The Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 includes the following “... increase in gross domestic product by 2030....optimization of sown areas for 2017-2020, rational use of land and water resources, introduction of modern intensive agricultural technologies2”. In the implementation of these tasks, including the chisel ripper and the device for laying mole drains, the processing of dense and gypsum interlayers in saline soils and increasing the efficiency of leaching saline lands are important tasks [5,6].

Review of foreign scientific research on the topic. Large-scale scientific research devoted to the development of resource-saving equipment and technologies to improve the reclamation state of lands and cost reduction methods is carried out in leading research centers and institutes, such as Texas A & M University (USA), Institute of Engineering Research (England), University of Bonn, Thullen Institute (Germany), The Swedish University of Agriculture Sciences (Sweden), Wageningen University (Holland), Senshu University (Japan), Hejiang Agricultural Research Institute (China), All-Russian Institute of Mechanization, Chelyabinsk Research Institute of Agricultural Mechanization and Electrification (Russia), Belarusian National Academy of Agricultural Mechanization (Belarus), Ukrainian Research Institute of Agricultural Mechanization (Ukraine), Kazakh Research Institute of Mechanization and Electrification (Kazakhstan).

As a result of the research carried out in the world on technologies for improving the reclamation state of lands and improving technical means, a number of results have been obtained, in particular, the following results: to ensure a reduction in energy consumption during deep loosening of the soil, loosening devices have been developed, through deformation of the soil, stretching it (Texas Agricultural & mexanical University, USA , Institute of Engineering Research (England); energy-saving technologies for loosening the solid layer of soil and carrying it out, having a 2-dimensional blade, baking powder (Wageningen University, Holland), developed pneumatic methods that loosen the soil under the action of air and improve its aeration, methods (The Swedish University of Agriculture Science, Sweden), an increase in plant yield by loosening the subsoil layer (University of Bonn, Thullen Institute, Germany), devices have been developed that form molehill drains by exploding gases in pasture lands (Sens hu University, Japan); (Hejiang Agricultural Research Institute, China); for the good development of the

root system of plants, loosening of the subsoil layer, dense and gypsum soil layers, technical tools have been developed for deep loosening (University of Hohenheim, University of Gottingen, Germany; University of Minnesota, USA; Center of Expertise and Transfer in Organic and Community Agriculture, France); developed technologies for deep processing of saline soils, salt washing (University Bologna, Institute for Agricultural mexanization, Italy, China Agricultural University, China); machines that form mole drains have been developed and their parameters have been substantiated and the technology for their application has been developed (All-Russian Research Institute of Mechanization, Chelyabinsk Research Institute of Mechanization and Electrification of Agriculture, Russia; Belarusian National Academy of Agricultural Mechanization, Belarus; Ukrainian Scientific and Research Institute of Agricultural Mechanization, Ukraine, Kazakh Research Institute of Mechanization and Electrification, Kazakhstan).

In the world, spending less energy, loosening the subsoil layer, dense and gypsum soil layers, qualitatively performing the technological processes of laying molehill drains, producing combined machines and technical means, improving the reclamation state of lands through deep loosening and forming molehill drains using the salt washing technology in in a number of, including the following sustainable areas, scientific research is being carried out: the development of deep loosening of the subsoil layer, the creation of machines that form molehill drains before washing saline lands and lands with a close location of subsoil groundwater, along with the fact that with deep loosening, the development of combined machines, processing the upper layers of the soil, improving the design of the working parts of chisel-rippers, developing working bodies with increased strength during deep loosening and the formation of molehills.

The degree of knowledge of the problem. On the creation of machines and technical means that cultivate the soil to improve the reclamation state of lands, the study of their change in agro-reclamation, water-physical properties under the influence of their working bodies and loosening, spending less energy, subarable and dense soil layers, as well as the development of theoretical and practical foundations for creating devices and technologies for improving the reclamation state of lands, were studied abroad by J.V.Stafford, F.E.Lowy, H.H.Tawlor, M.G. Huck, J.Balaton, H.J.Lut, R.D.Wismer, K.Kawanishi, K.Araya, L.Kosisira, A.J.Kolen, V.P.Goryachkin, V.A.Zheligovsky, A.N.Zelenin, G.N.Sineokov, V.V. Borodkin, V.G. Kiryukhin, A.N. Kostyakov, S.N. Rizhov, N.I. Bazilevich, E.I.

Pankova, I.S. Rabochev, V.M. N.G. Minashina, A.E. Nerozin, V.A. Kalantaev and others conducted research work.

In the Republic, G.M.Rudakov, R.I. Boymetov, M.M. Murodov, F.M. Mamatov, A.Tukhtakuziev, I.T.Ergashev, N.M.Murodov, N.S.Bibutov, O.R.Kenzhaev, Kh.R.Gaffarov, T.S.Khudoiberdiev, B.V.Khushvaktov, R.A.Abdurakhmonov, M.A. Akhmedzhanov, G.N.Kim and others, A.A. Rachinsky, N.F. Bepalov, K.M.Mirzazhonov, O.Ramazonov, F.M.Rakhimbaev, Kh.I.Yakubov, G.V.Eremenko, M.Kh.Khamidov, F.A.Baraev and others.

As a result of these studies, technologies and technical means have been developed for improving the reclamation state of lands, loosening subsoil layers, creating open and closed drainages, applied in agriculture and positive results have been achieved. However, in these studies, the issues of loosening dense and gypsum layers in order to improve the reclamation state of lands, the development of technology and technical means for creating molehill drains in saline and closely spaced subsoil groundwater lands have not been sufficiently studied.

Purpose of the study. Substantiation of the parameters of the working bodies of resource-saving chisel rippers for deconsolidation of dense and gypsumed soil layers and devices for laying molehill drains in the subsurface layers of saline soils and application technology, as well as improving the reclamation state of lands with their help.

Research objectives: development and justification of the design of a resource-saving chisel ripper that provides high-quality processing of dense and gypsum soil layers;

development of a device for creating mole drainages and their application technologies for improving the reclamation state of saline soils and closely located subsoil groundwater;

substantiation of the parameters of the working bodies of chisel rippers, loosening dense and gypsum soil layers, as well as devices laying molehill drainages in saline lands;

study of lands with a poor reclamation condition in the Bukhara region, for the use of a resource-saving chisel ripper and a device for laying mole drains;

study of the influence of the recommended technical means on the water-physical properties of the soil, as well as on the efficiency of washing salts in highly saline, dense and gypsum lands;

testing resource-saving chisel rippers and devices for laying mole drains and determining the economic efficiency of their use.

The object of study was dense, gypsum and saline lands, resource-saving chisel rippers used to improve the ameliorative state and install mole drains.

The subject of the study is the parameters of the working bodies of resource-saving chisel rippers and devices for laying mole drains, the processes of processing dense and gypsum soils, the boundary conditions of the regularities of the inflow of subsoil water to the mole drainage, the change in the regularities of the quality and energy indicators of chisel rippers and devices creating mole drains.

Research methods. When conducting research, methods of system analysis, fundamental laws and provisions of theoretical mechanics, higher mathematics and mathematical statistics were applied, methods of mathematical planning and strain measurement, as well as existing regulatory documents were used in the experiments (Tst 63.03.2001, Tst 63.04.2001), "Methodology for conducting field experiments" of the NIIKhSA and used recommendations for improving the ameliorative state of saline soils.

Results and discussion. In Uzbekistan, saline lands with poor ameliorative condition, with dense and gypsum layers and their use in agricultural production, problem statement, research objectives and conclusions are given. Full mechanization of land reclamation works is based on the corresponding optimal calculations of land reclamation machines, which ensures a reduction in labor costs and high quality of work. To perform land reclamation works, special land reclamation and agricultural machines are widely used.

The total area of irrigated land in the Bukhara region is 275,200 ha, of which 37,998 ha (13.8%) are not saline, 170,110 ha (61.9%) are low salinity, 60,054 ha (21.8%) are medium salinity, and highly saline soils - 6878 ha (2.5%).

In the course of the study, the hardness was studied in the areas freed from cotton before plowing, after processing with a chisel cultivator to a depth of 45 cm. It was found by experiments that the decrease in soil hardness in layers of 0-10 cm ranges from 1.98 MPa to 1, 03 MPa, in layers of 10-20 cm from 3.12 MPa to 1.4 MPa, in layers of 20-30 cm from 4.17 to 1.98 MPa, in layers of 30-40 cm from 4.27 MPa to 2, 62 MPa as well as in layers of 40-50 cm from 4.92 MPa to 3.27 MPa. In areas under alfalfa, the moisture content in soil layers 0-10, 10-20, 20-30, 30-40 and 40-50 cm is 8.15-9.07%, hardness is 1.89-5.12 MPa, and the density is 1.23-1.53 g/cm³. It can be seen that these values increased with increasing depth. The moisture content in the soil in cotton fields is 11.52-12.97%, hardness is 1.18-5.12 MPa, density is 1.37-1.68 g/cm³; in the sown

areas of wheat is 9.85-11.32%, 1.82-4.78 MPa and 1.38-2.74 g/cm³, respectively [7.8].

Dense and gypsum soil layers must be decompacted using a special technology, without mixing it with the fertile soil layer. Therefore, in order to study the force of traction resistance in the process of loosening, it is necessary to substantiate the parameters and shapes of the side profile of the rack.

Substantiation of the parameters and side profile of the working body of a resource-saving chisel ripper. The loosening working body in the process h of deconsolidation of gypsum soils at a depth t_g affects the gypsum layer with a thickness and on the soil layer with a thickness of, located under it, while the soil cracks without loosening not lower than the critical depth (h_k). During the movement of the working body, cracks appear on the gypsum layer without moving with the fertile soil layer (Rice.1).

a) cross section; b) longitudinal section

Rice. 1. The impact of the loosening working body on the soil.

It is enough only under the action of loosening paws to form cracks in the gypsum layer without completely deforming it. Based on this, the solution of the problem under consideration will be as follows: to perform the technological process of deformation, it is necessary to find such a shape of the side profile of the working body; in the process of work, it had a minimum traction resistance. The main vector of forces acting on point M , taking into account the fact that the soil crumbles on a curved elementary surface (ds) of the working body, has the following form [9,10]:

$$Qds = \rho_o \left[1 - \frac{y(M)}{H} \right] kv_o^n \cos^n \beta ds \quad (1)$$

here is ds an arbitrary surface of the element S ; M - internal point of the element ds ; H - depth of processing; k - coefficient taking into account loosening and resistance of the soil during movement; ρ_o - soil density, kg/m³; v_o^n - speed of

movement of the unit, m/s; β - coal between the normal force N and the speed of movement V of the soil particle, degree.

As a dynamic component of the resistance of the tractive effort or a component of the dynamic resistance, we take the dynamic pressure of the soil acting on the working body. We denote the dynamic component $\vec{Q}$ of the resistance force as and its elementary component $d\vec{Q}$, after appropriate transformations, we determine the shape of the side profile of the working rack.

The results of laboratory and field experiments showed that at $R = 0.20-0.24$ m, when processing gypsum and dense soil layers with an energy-saving chisel ripper to a depth of 0.40 m, it has a minimum traction resistance.

In the process of tillage with an unsatisfactory reclamation state and poor water-physical properties, it is important to study the change in soil properties as a result of the impact of working bodies on them.

With an increase in the radius of curvature and the speed of the unit, an increase in traction resistance was observed (Rice. 2).

Rice. 2. Change in traction resistance depending on the curvature of the radius (R) and the speed of the unit (V) at a processing depth of $H=0.45$ m and a strut out reach $L=0.210$ m.

The minimum traction resistance of the working bodies of the ripper chisel was observed, with the outreach of the rack $L = 0.210$ m, the working depth $H = 0.45$ m and the radius of curvature of the rack was $R = 0.20-0.25$ m, this explains It is due to the fact that there is less friction of the soil from the working surfaces of the rack.

With an increase in the speed of the unit from 1.10 m / s to 2.55 m / s, the traction resistance increased accordingly according to the parabola law.

The optimal parameters of the ripper chisel were determined using multivariate experiments.

According to the results of the experiment at $V=2.1$ m/s, the optimal parameters are: $H=0,45$ m; $L=0,210$ m; $R=0,230$ m; $b_{\pi}=0,15$ m and $\alpha = 27^{\circ}$.

Theoretical and technological foundations of the formation of mole-drainage in saline soils, the results of theoretical and experimental studies are described, which make it possible to substantiate the shape and dimensions of the working body of the drainage-mole device. In addition, in the course of theoretical studies during the formation of mole drains, soil stresses were studied. For this, nonlinear or linear equations of the mechanics of a deformable solid body were used during the motion of a liquid in a mole drainage [11].

Taking into account the elastic property of the medium, i.e. not taking into account the viscosity of the soil, it is possible to determine the radial and contour stresses as follows:

$$\sigma_r = A/r^2 + B; \quad \sigma_{\theta} = -A/r^2 + B \quad (2)$$

here σ_r - radial stress, N/m²; σ_{θ} - loop stress, N/m². A and B are random constants, which are determined using the boundary condition.

If the mole-drainage is formed at a depth of $y = -H$, the maximum stress in this case, under plane deformation, will be determined as follows [12]:

$$\sigma_r = \frac{B_S \gamma}{2k_r t g \phi} \left[e^{(k_r t g \phi (\frac{2H}{B_S}) - 1)} \right] + q e^{(k_r t g \phi (\frac{2H}{B_S}))} \quad (3)$$

here B_S - is the full width of the mole drainage, m; q - pressure force or pressure from the gravity of the soil, N/m²; in this case, the Christensen coefficient will be equal to $k_r = 1 + 2t g^2 \phi$.

When the drainage mole gun is operated to a depth of 0.6-0.7 m with flat soil deformation, the maximum stress will be equal $\sigma_r=1,30-1,40 \cdot 10^3$ κН/М².to = 1.30-1.40 103 kN/m.

The main parameters of drainage-mole tools, their indicators and values for medium soils: diameters of mole-drainage $d_m = 50 - 150$, mm; for stable soil $d_{\pi} = 100 - 300$ mm. These parameters are substantiated on the basis of theoretical and experimental studies (Fig. 4).

The parameters of the drainage-mole tool are determined using the following expressions: the length of the cylinder cone $\ell_{\text{ц}} = (1,5 - 2,0)d_m$; unit movement speed $\vartheta_{\text{с}} = 0,6 - 1,0$ m/s; length of steel cable $\ell_{\text{а}} \geq (0,1 - 0,15)$, m.

Depending on the length of the steel cable, the change in the traction resistance of the working bodies of the cylinder cone with a diameter of 0.105 m with a cable length of 0.30 m, the average value of the traction resistance was 5.1 kN.

Rice. 3. Drainage device mole gun.

1-cone-cylinder; 2-steel cable;

3-rack; 4-chisel; 5- movable frame; 6-hydraulic cylinder; 7-fixed frame.

In this process, a high-quality mole-drainage is formed, the filtration coefficient is 0.45 m / day. This is accepted as the best option for working bodies (Rice. 3).

During operation, the following forces act on the drainage mole tool [14,15]:

$$F_{\kappa d} = R_{rez} + F_{rkts} + F_{ktsp} + F_{st} + F_{sbp} + F_{kdbp} \quad (4)$$

here R_{rez} - is the resistance force when cutting the soil with a knife, N;

F_{rkts} - resistance force of the cone-shaped cylinder of the working body, N;

F_{ktsp} - resistance of the surface of a cone-shaped cylindrical Corps, N;

F_{st} - resistance of the steel cable connecting the working rack with body of a conical cylinder, N;

F_{sbp} - resistance force of soil sticking to the surface of the cone cylinder, N;

F_{kdbp} - resistance force due to soil adhesion to the surface of the conical cylinder tip, N.

The total traction power of the drainage mole tool during the working process is determined by the following expression:

$$N = \frac{F_{dt} \vartheta}{\eta} \quad (5)$$

Tool processing depth:

-H=40 cm; -H=50 cm; -H=60 cm.

Rice. 4. Change in traction resistance and soil filtration coefficient depending on the diameter of the cylinder cone.

$\eta = 0,75...0,80$ Efficiency of the drainage mole machine. On the basis of theoretical and experimental studies, during the operation of the drainage mole tool from external forces, the traction resistance is 9-11 kN, respectively, 7.5-13.5 kW of power is required.

With a diameter of 0.105 m of a cone-shaped cylinder, the filtration is 0.62-0.65 m/day (Rice. 4).

The difference between the results of theoretical and experimental studies in terms of filtration coefficients was 30-40%.

In addition, the filtration coefficient is influenced by such factors as the mechanical composition of the soil, the type of processing and their quality, etc. Experimental studies of research work on fields with a poor reclamation condition, with a salinity of 0.978% and with a heavy mechanical composition of the soil, where the location of the groundwater level is 1.0-1.2 m deep. Each field was divided into three sections. The first option is the control one (without loosening and drainage). In the second variant, the soil was loosened to a depth of 0.45 m and plowing was carried out to a depth of 0.35 m. In the third, plowing was carried out to 0.35 m and mole drainage at a depth of 0-0.60 m with a distance between drains of 2-3 m [16].

In the first field, the leaching rate is 4500 m³/ha, in the second field it is 5500 m³/ha, and in the third field it is 6500 m³/ha (Table 1).

Table 1
Results of the desalinization experiment

Indicators	Flush rate, m ³ /ha								
	4500			5500			6500		
Options	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Salt content, %	0,704	0,578	0,467	0,596	0,464	0,389	0,432	0,198	0,132
Desalinity factor	1,4	1,7	2,1	1,6	2,1	2,5	2,2	4,9	7,4

In field experiments, leaching rates were applied in winter: in the first field - in 2 cycles (that is, twice with a break of 1 month, approximately equal shares), in the second and third fields - in 3 cycles.

All three technology options, regardless of the leaching rate, showed a decrease in the salt content in the soil (Table 1). The best results were achieved in the third version of the technology, that is, with plowing and drainage. It is quite natural that the maximum effect was achieved at a leaching rate of 6500 m³/ha: the salt content decreased from 0.978% to 0.132%, the desalinization coefficient reached 7.4.

With the technology according to the third option, the duration of leaching irrigation is reduced by 15 days compared to the control, which ensures the timely start of spring agricultural work. In years with a sufficient amount of water, it is possible to carry out soil leaching at a rate of 6500 m³/ha, and in case of lack of water - at rates of 4500 or 5500 m³/ha against the background of loosening the soil to a depth of 0.45 m and mole drainage at a depth of 0-0.6 m which provide high washing efficiency.

In all 9 variants of experiments, the consumption of diesel fuel during plowing was approximately the same - 40-45 kg/ha. In the case of pre-treatment with chisel to a depth of 0.45, this indicator decreased to 38-42 kg/ha. In the third variant, with the additional work of the drainage-mole tool, the consumption of diesel fuel was even less - 35-38 kg/ha. For highly saline soils, the most economical in terms of water consumption and effective in terms of desalinization is considered to be the treatment option with a drainage mole tool [16].

To calculate the technical and economic efficiency of the developed tools with reasonable parameters, reference material was used for the economic

evaluation of agricultural machinery and machines. As calculations have shown, the use of a chisel ripper on soils with gypsum and dense layers, and a drainage mole tool on saline soils can reduce energy consumption by 9-14.5%, labor costs by 7.91-14.11%, operating costs for 8.16-11.0%, increase labor productivity by 16.3-18.0%, which is generally expressed in annual economic efficiency equal to 11.6-12.6 million soums.

Conclusions. The proposed design of the chisel subsoiler has the following optimal tool parameters: radius of curvature 0.23 m, stand reach 0.210 m; rack height 0.9-1.0 m; capture width of lancet paws 0.15 m; between the following working bodies 0.45-0.50 m, as well as the parameters of the drainage-mole tool such as the diameter of the cone-cylinder 0.105-0.110 m, the length of the steel cable 0.3-0.35 m, the width of the wave-shaped chisel 0.055-0.080 m angle of installation of working bodies 27-30° and the speed of movement of the unit 1.20-2.34 m/s and high-quality execution of the technological process for the removal of harmful salts from fertile soil layers is ensured.

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